

The Challenges of International Investment in Property Portfolio in a Depressed Economy: A Nigerian Experience

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ABSTRACT

International real estate investment especially in depressed economy has been an important discourse as it concerns Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). Depressed economies need to overcome their own challenges in the development process especially in the areas of capital accumulation and technological development. Again, it has been established that many real estate investors are increasingly looking to invest internationally for reasons of portfolio diversification and the search for higher risk adjusted returns than can be achieved in their domestic markets. This paper examines the challenges of international Investment in Property Portfolio in a depressed economy: the Nigerian experience. Among the challenges include Security Challenges, Political risk, Financing Risk (Banking Risk), Currency Risk, Ownership Structure Risk, Property Market Transparency, Land Registration Process and Transparency of Regulatory System. The paper advises that the Federal Government should work on the macro economy indices to stem most of the risk factors to make the investment arena conducive for international investors to operate profitably. Furthermore foreign investors need to partner with reliable domestic investors and Estate Surveyors and Valuers who are more familiar with the economy terrain to safeguard against losses.

Key Words: Challenges, International Investment, Property Portfolio, Depressed Economy

1.0 Introduction

International real estate investment is necessitated by real estate investors seeking to diversify risks inherent in such investments in their domestic markets. In the light of international real estate investment, financial globalization helped to create new investment vehicles which accelerates to solve many problems that are characterized by this asset class (Baum, 2008). International or cross-border property investment has boomed, and indirect property investment (investing through securities such as REITs, and through unlisted funds) has become common place.

International real estate investment through unlisted funds has included 'core' strategies, through which capital has been allocated largely to developed markets, and 'opportunity funds', which have also allocated capital to developing and emerging markets (Baum, 2009). This development has been a boom in listed real estate markets, especially in the Real Estate. Investment Trust (REIT) format, and in the number and value of unlisted property funds. The growth of the listed REIT market is largely a matter of public record, while investing in unlisted real estate vehicles has become an increasingly standard route to attaining international real estate exposure.

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Importantly, the change has had two main impacts: first, international property investment has boomed; second, indirect property investment (investing through securities and funds) has become the standard. The globalization of business activity was, prior to 2007-8, a continuing process, driven both by the conversion of ownership of successful companies from domestic to multi-national concerns, and by the increasing opportunities offered to corporations and institutional investors and banks to own overseas assets through globally-traded stock markets. The real estate investment (the construction of manufacturing facilities, for example) accounted for more than 40% of all foreign direct investment in the decade to 2001. Both occupier demand and the ownership of corporate real estate facilities have become increasingly driven by the needs of the multi-national enterprise

According to Property Funds Research data, of the top ten global investors seven have global real estate portfolios and the other three have announced plans to invest in global real estate for the first time. It is now unusual among large investors not to have a global property strategy. Currency hedging is, however, expensive and difficult to achieve efficiently (Lizieri, Worzala and Johnson, 1998) and vehicles are rarely fully hedged. This problem leaves investors at the mercy of currency movements. Other perceived difficulties, including the dangers of operating from a distance with no local representation, increases the attraction of investing internationally through liquid securitized vehicles and unlisted funds.

Also investing in a depressed economy is also a challenge for International Investment in Property Portfolio especially in Nigeria where economic depression continues to take its toll on the Nigerian economy, the country has witnessed a massive crash in the price of stocks and shares in the stock exchange market. Indeed, the real estate sector is not exempted from this economic situation.

This paper therefore examines the challenges of International Investment in Property Portfolio in a depressed economy: the Nigerian experience.

1.1 Economic depression

An **economic depression** is a period of carried long-term economic downturn that is the result of lowered economic activity in one major or more national economies (Krugman, P. 2010). Economic depression maybe related to one specific country where there is some economic crisis that has worsened but most often reflexes historically the American [Great Depression](#) and similar economic status that may be recognized as existing at some country, several countries or even in many countries. It is often understood in economics that economic crisis and the following recession that maybe named economic depression are part of economic cycles where the slowdown of the economy follows the economic growth and vice versa. It is a result of more severe economic problems or a downturn than the [recession](#) itself, which is a slowdown in economic activity over the course of the normal [business cycle](#) of growing economy (Krugman, P. 2010).

1.2 Distinction between a Depression and Recession

A recession and a depression describe periods during which the economy shrinks, but they differ in severity, duration, and scale (Ashe, S. and Kim, P., 2022).

A recession is considered a normal part of the boom-and-bust business cycle. It is generally defined as a decline in GDP for at least two consecutive quarters. Given the lag in collecting data on economic activity, a brief recession may be over before it is confirmed to have happened.

A depression lasts for years, and its consequences are far graver. Almost 25% of the U.S. population was unemployed during the depths of the Great Depression, and that figure does not include the farmers who lost their homes and their land due to cratering prices for their produce (Ashe, S. & Kim, P., 2022).

Recessions are much more common: Between 1854 and 2008, there were been 32 recessions in the U.S. and just one depression. Since then, they've had the Great Recession of 2008-2009 and the briefer and less disruptive covid recession of 2020.

- As noted, a recession is defined as at least two consecutive quarters of negative GDP growth, even if that decline is slight. It is a decline in economic activity spread across the economy that lasts more than a few months.
A depression is defined by a drop in annual GDP of 10% or more.

The Great Depression lasted for a decade.

- A recession is defined as two or more consecutive quarters of decline in GDP growth, no matter how slight the decline is. A depression is defined by a drop in annual GDP of 10% or more. It is a more extreme economic downturn, and there has only been one in American history: The Great Depression, which lasted from 1929 to 1939.

1.3 Example of a Depression

According to (Ashe, S. & Kim, P., 2022), the Great Depression is to this day the worst economic downturn in modern world history. Lasting roughly a decade, many historians trace its origins to Oct. 24, 1929, when the stock market crashed in an event afterward known as Black Thursday. After years of reckless investing and speculation, the stock market bubble burst and a huge sell-off began, with a then-record 12.9 million shares traded.

On that day, the United States was already in a recession. The following Tuesday, Oct. 29, 1929, the Dow Jones Industrial Average fell 12% more in another mass sell-off, triggering the start of the Great Depression.

The Great Depression began in the United States but soon took hold throughout the industrialized world. Its economic impact was felt for more than a decade. The era was characterized by catastrophic levels of unemployment, poverty, hunger, and political unrest. Consumer spending and business investment dried up. U.S. unemployment reached a level of

just under 25% in 1933 and remained in the double digits until 1941 when it finally fell to 9.66%.

During the Great Depression, wages dropped 42%, real estate prices declined 25%, total U.S. economic output fell by 30%, and many investors' portfolios became worthless as stock prices cratered.

Shortly after Franklin D. Roosevelt was elected president in 1932, the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC) was created to protect depositors' bank accounts in the event of bank failure.

1.4 Economic Depression in Nigerian real estate

Economic depression is a recurrent issue because of the cyclical nature of the global economy. That is why most countries, especially the developed ones, often diversify the structural base of their economy to withstand any external shock (Farayibi, 2016). Economic depression although sometimes called recession is often characterized by rising prices of goods and services, inability of government to meet its financial obligations, exchange rate fluctuations, and poor performance of other macroeconomic variables which defines the state of the economy per time. Economic depression is a tragedy.

Sanusi, (2008) states that the Real Estate sector is envisioned as one of the major drivers of the economy with 5% increase in GDP growth, other sectors like health, education, transportation and the likes depend heavily on the Real Estate industry. However, the Real Estate industry can be fractioned into three crucial parts which are the Residential Sector, Commercial sector and Industrial sector which employs a lot of labor Provision of mega facilities, structures and infrastructure projects have been the exclusive responsibility of the government, it is considered as a social and political responsibility of government to provide basic services to the citizens. Thus, the consistent failure of the governments in Africa to provide adequate services is partly because African governments lack the money and resources to maintain and expand existing infrastructures. El-Rufai (2011) contended that infrastructure is essential to human and economic development and is the catalyst for magnetizing investment, for which Nigeria has requisite potentials. For example, the Real Estate sector experienced dynamic growth of about 12.09% in 2010, compared to 11.97% in 2009, thus reflecting more preponderant investments in both residential and non residential buildings and other construction activities. In the same vein, the Real Estate related activities experienced a growth of 12.24% in 2010 as compare to 11.97% in 2009. This is because in 2010 some large projects were executed which positively impacted the performance of the sector. Some of these projects includes: dredging of River Niger, rehabilitation of national roads having a total of 1,975 km, railway lines, Public Private Partnership (PPP) projects, Presidential Initiative Projects integrating up to 853.82 km of roads and several housing unit types (Oluwakiyesi, 2011).

Nigeria as a nation went into recession in 2016 as a result of continuous fall in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country and in 2020 the Nigerian economy shrank by 1.8%, its deepest decline since 1983. During this period, the real estate market is one of the most hit sectors of the economy. It is important to examine the impact of the economic downturn on the

real estate market in Nigeria, a topical issue that presents significant challenges to almost all economies (underdeveloped, developing and developed). In recent times, the drop in oil prices has left nations with undiversified oil based economy like Nigeria in economic crisis. This challenge, brought about by exchange rate fluctuations has led to the devaluation of the Naira, affecting the demand and supply sides of the economy. This economic downturn has hit the Nigerian real estate market in a unique way.

As economic depression continues to take its toll on the Nigerian economy, the country has witnessed a massive crash in the price of stocks and shares in the stock exchange market (Kabaka, B.S & Ekwuru, E., 2022). Indeed, the real estate sector is not exempted from this economic situation. It is common knowledge that one of the most notable hallmarks of a recession is the scarcity of funds. This is further worsened by the fluctuation in the value of the Naira against the Dollar/Pounds. This fluctuation has made it difficult for some people to consider the possibility of investing in real estate at this time. Even those who are willing to invest are faced with the burden of finding investment opportunities in markets that offer the greatest long term growth and stability. It is thus safe to say that, with the current low investment in the real estate sector, which has seen housing prices dropping at near historical lows; this may be the perfect time to invest in real estate (Perchstone and Graeys, 2016).

1.5 Causes of Economic Depression in Nigeria

Haruna (2017) proposed 14 factors are responsible for the recession or Depression Nigeria is currently undergoing:

1. Poor economic planning: Poor economic planning and no concrete implementation of its economic planning is the major cause of Nigeria current recession. The government has proclaimed the usual generalities that every government indulges itself in about Diversifying the economy, Improving manufacturing/mining sector, Raising agricultural output, Encouraging foreign investment, among others, yet no concrete evidenced strategic plan for growth. No doubt, the government has taken some steps like the elimination of dollar purchase privileges for importers of 40 items such as-rice, cement, toothpicks, private planes, poultry, meat, margarine, wheelbarrows, textiles and soaps.
2. High Inflation Rate: Government banning the importation of certain essential agricultural products like rice without considering gestation period is error. Removal of fuel subsidy shouldn't be simultaneously with the banning of these agricultural products. Nigeria inflation rate currently stands at 22.96%, which is extremely high.
3. High Interest Rate: Interest rate is between 17-18.75%. Is extremely high for investors. This high interest rate is discouraging investors. The poor investment culminates into high rate of unemployment in the country.
4. High Taxation: It is only in Nigeria that you see government charging high tax rate during economic recession. Small businesses are slaughtered with high interest rate. Both high interest and tax rate has lowered Nigeria aggregate demand.
5. Policy conflict: The economic policies appear conflicting. How? High-interest rate, high tax rate are tight monetary policy measures. But government told the public it is adopting expansionary policy-budget deficit.
6. Overdependence of the nation on petroleum as a source of income, Nigeria gets over 95% of its revenue from oil (Sanusi, 2001).

7. Resource mismanagement (not just petroleum, but natural gas as well), countries like Malaysia and Singapore in the 1970s had the same revenue with Nigeria but today make more than 11 times the revenue of Nigeria.
8. High Rate of Importation: This has been a great menace to the Nigerian economy as many commodities are imported and on the long run other economies benefit from Nigeria. For example, many electronic products are imported from China.
9. The Debt Game: Nigeria as a country is still heavily indebted to the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) and wealthy countries.
10. The Changing Dynamics of over Population has also affected the Nigerian economy because adequate plan have not been put in place for the nation's increasing population.
11. Outright Corporate Greed exhibited by various companies and service providers also has a major contribution to the economic situation in the country.
12. The national relocation of employment and the changing of means of labor also have a part. Many people are migrating to major cities like Lagos, Abuja, Port Harcourt causing these cities to be overpopulated and few people left to farm in the other states.
13. Growing gap between the elite and the impoverished also has its fair share on the nation's economic meltdown. Other factors are the erosion of human dignity, the erosion of dignity of life etc.
14. Other factors: these include ethno-religious crises, political instability, fraud, leadership crises, disease burden, budget priority and implementation etc.

2.0 Nigeria

2.1 Country overview

Nigeria is in the Western part of Africa, in the gulf of guinea and occupies a total land area of about 923,768 sq.km, with estimated population of 223.8million people according to world gazette (2023). It is the 8th largest country in terms of population and the 32nd largest country in the world in land mass (World Bank, 2010). It shares borders with Benin Republic in the West, Niger and Chad on the north and Cameroon on the East, on the South is approximately 85km of coastline to the Atlantic Ocean. On this coast line is the Niger Delta basin of the south which has the largest River deltas in the world and is the convergence of the two major rivers in the country: the River Niger, which runs from the West, and the River Benue which runs from the East.

There are roughly three climatic regimes in the country: the tropical rainforest of the far south, the desert like climate of the far north and the savannah which accounts for everywhere else. The majority of the country falls in the last region: with a long wet season in the south, particularly the south-east, and a shorter wet season in the north (Economic intelligence unity, 2012).

The country has English language as an official language and about 250 ethnic groups with more than 500 indigenous languages making it one of the most ethnically diverse Nations in the world. Three main ethnicities dominate: the Fulani/Hausas of the North (speaks Hausa language); the Igbos of the South East (speaks Igbo language); and the Yorubas of the South-West (speaks Yoruba) and they together account for about 70% of the population and these are official recognized indigenous languages. Other ethnic groups include the Ijaw, Edo, Kanuri, Ibibio, Ebira, Nupe, Urhobo, Tiv etc which collectively make up the remaining 30% of the populace. Religion in the country is primarily Christianity and Islam with a small minority of a variety of

traditional deity worshippers. In particular, the Hausa/Fulani tribe of the North are Muslims, the Ibo tribe of the South-East and other minority tribes of the South-South are Christians, and the Yoruba tribe of the South-West are a mixture of Christians and Muslims. The country has been under democratic dispensation since 1999, with Civil and Environmental Research.

President Bola Ahmed Tinubu as the president and commander-in chief of armed forces, since 29th May 2023 till date. The country runs a presidential system adopted from the United States of America. It has a bicameral legislative arms-of senate (the upper chamber) and the House of Representatives (the lower chamber). The country is made of 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory.

2.2 Globalization of Real Estate Providers

Global real estate has become an asset class for foreign individual and institutional investors seeking to diversify their investment portfolios. On the other, a suite of intergenerational migration and education plans may also be motivating foreign investors. Government and public responses to the latest manifestation of global real estate investment have taken different forms. These range from pro-foreign investment, primarily justified on geopolitical economic grounds, to anti-foreign investment for reasons such as mitigating public dissent and protecting the local housing market.

Foreign investment in residential real estate is re-emerging as a key political issue in several Anglo-sphere and Asian countries. The global real estate activities of the Four Asian Tiger countries (i.e., Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea and Taiwan) in Anglo-sphere markets in the 1980s are well documented. The increasing foreign investor activity of new middle-class and super-rich investors from Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (known collectively as the BRICS) in global real estate markets has introduced or revived some deep-seated cultural and political sensitivities (Rogers, Lee, & Yan, [2015](#)).

Government and public responses to the latest manifestation of global real estate investment has taken different forms. On the back of the well-reported rise in Chinese investment in local real estate in Australia, for example, in 2014, the Federal Government conducted a parliamentary inquiry into individual foreign investment in residential real estate. In Canada, under mounting pressure to take action on housing affordability, the government reviewed their investment visa programme. In London, a 300-strong group of protestors picketed against foreign real estate investment outside The World Property Market international real estate event. Meanwhile, European Union countries such as Spain, Greece, Cyprus and Turkey have introduced visa schemes targeting investors from Asia, Russia and North America in an attempt to attract global capital to their local real estate markets. In Asia, the Chinese government tightened up foreign investment rules for real estate in 2010, and the Singaporean and Hong Kong governments introduced staged 'cooling measures' with implications for foreign investment in real estate beginning in 2009 and 2010, respectively. In the fluid regulatory environment in Hong Kong, the government suspended their Capital Investment Entrant Scheme in January 2015.

Within this changing global context, the six articles in this special issue on the globalisation of real estate present a diverse range of empirical case studies from Canada, Hong Kong, Singapore, Russia, Australia and Korea. David Ley ([2015](#)) examines the impact of international

real estate investment on the local housing market in Vancouver, Canada. Choon-Piew Pow (2016) exposes the strategies that are used by investors and the government in Singapore to create and seek out new safe havens within which to 'park' and 'grow' super-rich wealth. Karita Kan (2016) moves beyond culturally essentialist analyses of global real estate transactions to show how Hong Kong investors have made inroads into the Mainland Chinese market. This analysis draws attention to geopolitical questions at the abstract level of the nation-state as well as the more embodied level on the ground. Büdenbender, M., & Golubchikov, O. (2016) article also considers geopolitical questions. It demonstrates that global real estate and property markets play an increasingly important role in international relations, and in this Russian case study, foreign investment has emerged as a form of soft geopolitical power. Hyung Min Kim's (2016) article shows how foreign investment is organised socio-spatially in Seoul, Korea. In this case, a knowledge of local conditions, which is often built through previous residency or a shared ethnicity, is important in shaping the spatial distribution of foreign investment in the city. Finally, Alexandra Wong focuses on Mainland Chinese foreign real estate investments into Sydney's Chinatown district, with Chinatown being an important global-urban node within the emerging Chinese foreign real estate market in Sydney.

3.0 Challenges of International Investment in Property Portfolio in a Depressed Economy : A Nigerian Experience.

Despite the potential of real estate to attract foreign direct investment to Nigeria, there are a number of challenges that international investors face, just like most depressed economies. Generally speaking, the more uncertain the returns are in a market, the higher the risk associated with the investment. While this is true in any real estate investment, the factors of this risk are escalated in foreign market when political, legal and currency factors come into play. The following challenges are faced by foreign investors in Nigeria

3.1 Security Challenges

Insecurity is a significant challenge facing international real estate investment in Nigeria. The country is plagued by frequent incidents of kidnapping, armed robbery, and terrorism. Terrorist attacks, Bandits, separatist movements, kidnappings, and killings have discouraged investors. Boko Haram sects terrorized the North East, Bandits terrorized the South East, South West, North West and North Central, while Niger Delta militants hold swage in the South-South, bombing and blowing off oil pipe lines. Buildings are destroyed and probability of rebuilding by investors is very slim for obvious reason – fear of repeated attacks. The risk assessment in the regions is very high

These security challenges have made it difficult for developers/foreign investors to secure their properties and have caused delays in the construction process. The cost of security personnel and equipment has also increased due to the high risk of theft and vandalism.

3.2 Political risk

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Many foreign investors consider political risk to be one of the most determinants in real estate decision (Ganster, 2007). Country risk analysis involves an examination of the country's economic outlook and stability of its government, as well as factors including corruption and crimes. The Nigerian government has a reputation for being unpredictable, and there is a risk of sudden policy changes that could affect investors. Lovells (2013) and Agu et al. (2013) write that political instability and violence have killed the interest of both domestic and foreign investors in Nigeria.

3.3 Financing Risk (Banking Risk)

Another major challenge of international real estate investment in Nigeria is the banking system. Just like most of other emerging market economies, the country's bank lending is relatively inefficient even though it is the most common source of financing for both domestic and foreign investors. Nigeria bank lending rate has been fluctuating over the years and hovers between 15-20%. This high cost of finance is a serious impediment to international real estate investors. Nigeria mortgage industry is still underdeveloped. This is evidenced by statistics from World Bank. Between 1960 and 2009, its transaction profile stands at less than 100,000 (Emiedafe, 2015).

The contribution of mortgage financing to Nigeria GDP is almost zero with real estate contributing 5% and mortgage loans and advances contributing 0.5%. Alfred (2014) posits that finance sector risk is a great worry to foreign real estate investors to Nigeria. Omisore (2012) posits that Nigerian real estate sector lacks well-defined and reliable mortgage financing as it is seen not being affordable to support longer terms loans and funding. The Federal Mortgage bank and its subsidiary are the only mortgage institutions in Nigeria funding real estate investment and the cue to access the fund is unending. Therefore investors must move capital for investment into the country. The cost of such transfer may be huge considering the processes involved in the country.

3.4 Currency Risk

The risk of currency devaluation is a threat to the stability of dollar denominated returns. Many Latin America markets have had a history of volatile currency fluctuation, and consequently devaluation remains a real risk. Currency risk is readily applicable to Nigeria since 1986, when the government of President Babangida devalued naira the country's local currency. The exchange rate of naira stood at #914 to \$1 and could rise to #1300 to \$1 in the black market. (Key indicators, 2023), and it is expected to worsen over the years. Additionally, Nigeria has some legal restriction on the transfer abroad of funds associated with capital employed in an investment and this perhaps is one of the greatest risks mitigating investment in Nigeria. The country's currency risk is consequently rated (CCC) and that pose a challenge to international real estate investors.

3.5 Ownership Structure Risk

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The right to own or use land is a prevalent issue in many emerging markets economies. National and local governments still own a vast majority of land in many emerging markets, requiring investors to structure long term leases, a risk that some institutional investors have trouble accepting. In Nigeria, the current law guiding the use and ownership of real estate is the Land Use Act of 1978 (Cap 202 laws of the federation of Nigeria, 1990).

The Act vested all land in the territory of each state in Nigeria in the Governor of that State who holds it in trust and administered for the use and common benefit of all Nigerians. The Act also stipulates that all land in the urban areas shall be under the control and management of the Governor while other land shall be under the control and management of the local government of which the land is situated. The implications of this is that individual has only possessory rights, thus individual are only entitle to right to occupancy covered by statutory or customary certificate of occupancy issued by Governor of a state or a local government chairman for land in urban area or land in rural areas respectively. These statutory or customary rights of occupancy are not easy to get, hence most properties do not have perfect titles. Generally speaking, acquisition of property and perfection of the title documents are tedious, cumbersome and costly in the country. Another challenge is the power vested by the Act to the government to revoke right of occupancy for overriding public interest. The Act stipulated that the holders or owners of the right of occupancy will only be entitled to compensation for economic crops, trees and other unexhausted improvements and there is no compensation for land.

Yet another challenge arising from this is the issue of consent. For real estate development transactions, banks looks at the subject land as collateral, but the transaction is put at risk because of the myriad of problems under the Act. The banks are required to obtain a consent which they do at very heavy costs. The original title documents which the banks place safely in their vaults may turn out to be worthless, if the Governor announcement to withdraw such certificate of occupancy is carried out. Thus, many investors consider Nigeria property rights to be at considerable risk for real estate investment.

3.6 Property Market Transparency

One of the greatest contrasts in developed and emerging markets is the difference in “transparency”, which refers to the quality and quantity of the information made available to participants, as well as the consistency of the rules and regulations with respect to property rights in the market (Udobi, Kalu and Elekwachi, 2016). There is a high transparency in the property markets in such countries likes the United States of America and United Kingdom with an easy flow of information and its reliability, but also makes it harder to find market inefficiencies that would earn a “risk premium”. On the other hand, low transparency imposes additional risks and transaction costs.

According to JLL’s latest global real estate transparency index 2020, Nigeria ranked 68 out of 99 countries under review reveals continued progress in transparency over the past few years. Over 80% of markets have registered an improvement since 2012, although typically, increases in most markets have not been great. There transparency score reflects the lack of reliable current market statistics (including investment performance indexes and market data), as well as a weak

record for property rights. There is also no requirement to report sale or transfers of property, and therefore many real estate transactions are not transparent to the market.

3.7 Land Registration Process

International real estate investors need security to access mortgage fund. Such security must necessarily be registered both at the co-operate affairs commission and the Land Registry to give it legal backing (Lovells, 2013). According to World Bank Doing Business Report (2012), Nigeria is ranked 182 out of 185 countries. She is among the worst in land registration. The process can take up to 12 processes, last between six months to one year and cost about 20.8% of the property value. Developers are usually frustrated and sometimes lose their source of funding or incur further costs in interest on bank loans (Emiedafe, 2015).

3.8 Transparency of Regulatory System

In an effort to encourage FDI, Nigeria introduced the Nigeria Investment Promotion Commission Decree No.15 of 1995. This Decree makes it possible for foreign investors to invest in any part of the Nigerian economy with or without Nigerian partners. This attracted a foreign direct investment (FDI) of \$723.49 million to the country in 2015. However, despite the current administration's effort to make government more transparent, corruption in Nigeria seems to have not been reduced. For real estate developers, the corruption often translates into inconsistencies in the building codes, building approvals and documentations, increasing the uncertainty and risk associated with the investment. In a nutshell, international real estate investors is faced with challenges arising from weak property rights, regulatory inconsistencies, low transparency, currency risk, political policy inconsistencies and unstable banking system.

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper has successfully discussed the challenges facing the International Investment in Property Portfolio in a depressed economy (Nigerian). Most of the risk factors are inherent in the macro economy of Nigeria. The government at the center has a lot to do to ameliorate the challenges raised. The exchange rate of the naira has to be stabilized as it now changes daily, the double digit inflation rate, even though is a blessing to investors in the short run because of strong demand, will erode the real return of investors in the long run. The regulatory laws must be streamlined and handled by few specific agencies. Processes of land registration must be overhauled and made to function effectively and timely.

Federal Government is already on security matters but more need to be done to ensure complete safety for foreign investors. Bilateral treaties on mitigation of repatriation of investment proceeds and other related matters should be ratified, accepted into Nigerian domestic laws and adopted by Nigerian government.

These done, Nigeria foreign real estate investment terrain will be safer for investors to achieve their diversification benefits.

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